

Time Management and Work Environment as Correlates of Lecturers' Productivity in Colleges of Education in Osun State

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Abstract:

The study examined time management and work environment as correlates of lecturers' productivity in Colleges of Education in Osun State. Specifically, the study examined the relationship between time management and lecturers' productivity; and work environment and lecturers' productivity in Colleges of Education. The descriptive research of the survey type was adopted in this study. The sample size for this study was 140 respondents selected from two Colleges of Education in Osun State using multistage sampling procedure. The data for this study were collected through the use of two sets of self - designed questionnaire tagged Time Management and Work Environment Questionnaire (TMWEQ) and Lecturers' Productivity Questionnaire (LPQ). The face and content validity of the instruments (TMWEQ and LPQ) were validated by specialists in Educational management as well as Tests and Measurement experts. A reliability coefficient of 0.81 was obtained for Time Management and Work Environment Questionnaire (TMWEQ) and 0.85 was obtained for the Lecturers' Productivity Questionnaire (LPQ). The responses obtained were collated and analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings of the study revealed that time management and work environment were related to lecturers' productivity in Colleges of Education. It was recommended among others that Colleges of

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Educational management should place more emphasis on improving the work environment of lecturers through provision of modern facilities, conducive office, teaching resources among others.

Keywords: Time Management, Work Environment, Lecturers, Productivity,

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Introduction

Colleges of Education, like any other tertiary institutions relies on its employees who work to stir up the activities of the organization in order to achieve its objectives. These employees are regarded as most important and tangible assets in the organization (Onyeizugbe & Orogbu, 2015). It is a popular knowledge that no institution will grow beyond the quality of human resources that constitute the teaching and non-teaching staff. This is because productivity lies within the employees' ability and commitment as well as initiatives to improve the sustainability of the institution, which are often ratified by management (Maha, 2015).

Productivity is the measurement of actual output or result against set goals (Kazimoto, 2016). According to the framework for measuring the lecturers' productivity, it is measured based on his/her research output, quality of teaching, community services among others. Lecturers are the greatest assets as well as major stakeholders in the Colleges of Education. Their main duty is to teach and bring up the young generation of students to acquire health related skills and knowledge for growth and development. Teaching is a difficult task and demands serious commitment to be effective.

Lecturers' productivity in Colleges of Education can be considered as the teaching of the students, amount of research conducted, community services rendered by the staff. In support of this, Goodall (2013) posited that research is one of the focal points on which the tertiary education rests while others include teaching and community service. Research productivity of lecturers is mainly disseminated through publication and this earns the staff local and global recognition.

The researcher observed that lecturers' productivity in Colleges of Education appears to be very low. It appears some lecturers of Colleges of Education no longer place priority on their primary role, which is teaching. In the aspect of teaching, the researcher observed that some lecturers appear not to be punctual in classroom while some who are punctual do not go to classroom to teach. It was observed that some lecturers no longer use instructional materials for teaching while some appear not to have good mastery of the subject matter.

Research publication seems to be considered as one of the major determinants of lecturers' productivity. The principal criterion for promoting lecturers from one level to the other is research output or publications in referred national and international journals and text books. However, the researcher observed that most lecturers in Colleges of Education do not conduct independent study for publication. Some lecturers have been observed not to render selfless consultancy services to communities and agencies among others. The importance of teaching, research, and community services cannot be overemphasised among lecturers in Colleges of Education.

The observed low lecturers' productivity in Colleges of Education could be attributed to so many factors among which are poor work environment and time mismanagement. The extent of lecturers' productivity in their primary responsibility most often may not be guaranteed in the face of time mismanagement and poor work environment.

Time is a precious good to both employees and employers in a modern organization. Time management has been defined as cluster of behavioural skills sets that are important in an organization (Abu, 2015). Time is one of the resources that lecturers need to manage efficiently in order to be productive. The lecturers who coordinate the activities of students

must be able to manage his time very well in order to accomplish the stated aims and objectives. Time represent the human age in general, a critical resource in management, the ability to manage time and organize it is the key to success for any business.

Time management depends on the ability of a person to analyze his time and knowledge of where and how he spends and the leader who cannot manage his time cannot manage anything else (Omar, 2016). Time management skills include activities performed by lecturers such as planning in advance, lectures preparations and prioritizing. Omar (2016) also opined that time management skills require four basic steps: decide what you want to accomplish; determine activities to reach each goal; make a daily 'to do' list; and set one's priorities every day.

Time management is actually a form of self-management as it requires and enables lecturers to control or manage events. Time management thus requires the right decision at the right time and is one of the basic requirements of personal and professional success. Time Management is one of the branches of educational management that is interested in investing time and making use of it as efficiently and efficiently as possible, reducing the chances of wasting it and exploiting it by increasing the productivity of workers at a specific time (Abu, 2021).

It has been however observed that the most common difficulties encountered by some lecturers in Colleges of Education are their inability to organize and plan their work properly. It is not uncommon to see lecturers usually coming late to work when there are pressing issues waiting for them in their offices. It has also been observed by the researcher that some lecturers attend to issues that should have been handled after their official hours at work. Such issues include unnecessary personal phone calls, wasting much time with visitors, involving in routines that should have been delegated.

Work environment can be referred to as elements within the work place, such as management style, inter- relationship among staff and opportunity to develop oneself. An improved work environment could result in a reduction in a number of complaints and absenteeism and will bring an increase in productivity. Work environment can be perceived as those processes, systems, structures, tools or conditions in the workplace that influence favourably or unfavourably individual employee performance. In addition, work environment encompasses policies, rules, culture, resources, working relationships, work location, and internal and external environmental factors, all of which influence the ways employees perform their job functions (Famade, et al., 2016).

Teachers use about 40 percent of their existence within work environments, which extremely affect their status of mind, aptitudes, and actions in addition to their productivity (Bukola & Owolabi, 2015). An understanding of the effect of work environment on the productivity of lecturers cannot be over-emphasized or seen as overstatement in every organization. Experience has shown that workers are directly influenced by the environment they find themselves in terms of productivity if the environment is not conducive. However, poor work environment has posed a great danger to workers health and therefore make them to work with less joy and enthusiasms and work progress is hampered and disrupted.

The absence of important of work materials as a result of non-availability of some necessary office facilities like air condition, rugs or tiles, good ventilation in some of the department in Colleges of Education is a common feature of poor work environment. Some offices or

departments look depressing and unstimulating. Some of them have no louvers, light and some with uncompleted roofs. The state of affairs seems not compete favourably with offices found in Universities and other tertiary institutions, some of the offices are with dirty and scattered environment, most of the departments have small floor space with materials tables, chairs, papers, files and other things scattered here and there.

It appears that if an organization provides its employees with better work and most conducive working environment they will perform exceptionally well with enhanced productivity. However, the researcher observed that the work environment of lecturers in Colleges of Education seem not to be conducive. There are situations whereby four to five lecturers shares the same office. There are inadequate infrastructures needed in the office, like table, chairs and other materials. Aside the facility aspect, policies that are not too workers' friendly are usually set by management. The researcher observed that some lecturers usually complain about their work environment as one of the factors affecting their productivity.

The problem of the study is to examine how time management and work environment are related to lecturers' productivity in Colleges of Education in Osun State. The study examined time management and work environment as correlates of lecturers' productivity in Colleges of Education in Osun State. Specifically, the study examined:

- i. the relationship between time management and lecturers' productivity in Colleges of Education; and
- ii. the relationship between work environment and lecturers' productivity in Colleges of Education.

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were generated to guide the study:

1. There is no significant relationship between time management and lecturers' productivity in Colleges of Education in Osun State.
2. There is no significant relationship between work environment and lecturers' productivity in Colleges of Education in Osun State.

Research Method

The descriptive research of the survey type was adopted in this study. The population for the study was all the lecturers in Colleges of Education in Osun State. The sample size for this study was 140 respondents selected from two Colleges of Education in Osun State. The sample was selected using multistage sampling procedure and three stages were involved.

The data for this study were collected through the use of two sets of self – designed questionnaire. The first one is tagged Time Management and Work Environment Questionnaire (TMWEQ) which was administered on the lecturers. It consisted of two sections A and B. Section A sought for the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents while section B consisted of 20 items on time management and work environment. The items in the questionnaire were on a 4-point likert type scale with four options ranging from Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree: Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2) and Strongly Disagree (1).

The second one tagged Lecturers' Productivity Questionnaire (LPQ) was administered on the Head of Department of each of the lecturers. It comprises three sections A, B and C Section A contains items on the bio – data of the Heads of Departments. Section B contained items on

the bio – data of the lecturers to be assessed and was completed by the researcher while section C consisted of 20 items which elicited information on job productivity. The items in the questionnaire were on a rating scale with five options ranging from Excellent to Poor: Excellent (5), Very Good (4), Good (3), Fair (2) and Poor (1).

The face and content validity of the instruments (TMWEQ and LPQ) were validated by specialists in Educational management as well as Tests and Measurement experts. The instruments were said to have facial relevance and concerned with the subject matter it claimed to measure. The reliability of the instruments was carried out using the test re-test method. The Time Management and Work Environment Questionnaire (TMWEQ) was administered twice within an interval of two weeks on 20 lecturers in a College of Education that will not be included in the sampled Colleges of Education for the study while Lecturers' Productivity Questionnaire (LPQ) was administered twice within an interval of two weeks on Heads of Departments of the selected 20 lecturers. The instruments were administered twice within a period of two weeks. The scores from the two sets of responses were correlated using Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis to obtain the reliability coefficients of the instruments. A reliability coefficient of 0.81 was obtained for Time Management and Work Environment Questionnaire (TMWEQ) and 0.85 was obtained for the Lecturers' Productivity Questionnaire (LPQ). The coefficients were considered high enough for the reliability.

The responses obtained were collated and analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Hypotheses 1 – 2 were tested using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation (PPMC). All the hypotheses formulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between time management and lecturers' productivity in Colleges of Education in Osun State.

In testing this hypothesis, data on time management were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section B of TMWEQ (item 1 – 10) in the questionnaire. Data on lecturers' productivity were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section C of LPQ (item 1 – 20) in the questionnaire. Both were compared for statistical significance using Pearson Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 levels. The result is presented in table 1.

Table 1: Relationship between time management and lecturers' productivity

Variables	N	Mean	Stand Dev	r-cal	P-value
Time Management	140	29.37	2.78	0.428*	0.000
Lecturers' Productivity	140	71.20	4.19		

*P<0.05

Table 1 showed that the r-cal value of 0.428 is significant at 0.05 level of significance because the P-value (0.000) < 0.05. The null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is significant relationship between time management and lecturers' productivity in Colleges of Education in Osun State. Time management is moderately and positively related to lecturers' productivity.

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between work environment and lecturers' productivity in Colleges of Education in Osun State.

In testing this hypothesis, data on work environment were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section B of TMWEQ (item 11 – 20) in the questionnaire. Data on lecturers' productivity were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section C of LPQ (item 1 – 20) in the questionnaire. Both were compared for statistical significance using Pearson Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 levels. The result is presented in table 2.

Table 2: Relationship between work environment and lecturers' productivity

Variables	N	Mean	Stand Dev	r-cal	P-value
Work Environment	140	24.17	2.05	0.571*	0.000
Lecturers' Productivity	140	71.20	4.19		

*P<0.05

Table 2 showed that the r-cal value of 0.571 is significant at 0.05 level of significance because the P-value (0.000) < 0.05. The null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is significant relationship between work environment and lecturers' productivity in Colleges of Education in Osun State. Work environment is moderately and positively related to lecturers' productivity.

Discussion

The findings of the study revealed that there was significant relationship between time management and lecturers' productivity in Colleges of Education in Osun State. The implication of this finding is that proper time management will positively influence productivity of lecturers in Colleges of Education. In consonance with this finding, Sarpong – Nyavor (2012) revealed that there was a positive relationship between planning and employees' performance. Omenu (2015) concluded that setting priorities as a time management skill influenced productivity. Khan, Khan, Din and Khan (2016) concluded that time management could improve job productivity.

The findings of the study also revealed that there was significant relationship between work environment and lecturers productivity in Colleges of Education in Osun State. Ojogwu and Alutu (2009) and Olatunji (2013) alluded that for proper teaching and learning to take place, there must be adequate infrastructure and in many schools in Nigeria, the facilities provided for most departments are grossly inadequate for teachers or practicals, some teachers have no offices, the classroom spaces are small and do not permit meaningful interaction between the teachers and the students which makes the academic environment unhealthy, with decayed, dysfunctional, and dilapidated infrastructural facilities. The study of Owoeye and Olatunde (2011) established that school environment were the most potent determinant of job productivity.

Idemobi and Onyeizugbe (2011) concluded that work environment has significant effect on employees' performance and productivity. Bukola and Owolabi (2015) posited that teachers are not expected to be effective or perform at high level in the area of curriculum without the adequate basic infrastructure and facilities for teaching and learning.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it is concluded that time management and work environment are determinants of lecturers' job productivity.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made.

1. Colleges of Educational management should place more emphasis on improving the work environment of lecturers through provision of modern facilities, conducive office, teaching resources among others.
2. Lecturers should improve on their time management as this could go a long way improve job productivity
3. Job productivity of lecturers should be annually appraised and proper feedback should be given back to them so as to know the areas improvements are needed.

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